

Proof of Concept of Amoxicillin Through the Looking-Glass: A Computational Sight on Structural Aspects of Mirror Life

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Disclaimer: This research, its methods, and outcomes are meant to provide an evolving open forum for cumulative research and discussion on the risks associated with mirror microorganisms

This document file includes:

- Overview of the proof-of-concept study
- Details about the methods applied
- Details about the outcome

Raw data made available:

- 3D model of mirror image of amoxicillin's target
- Calculated binding architecture of amoxicillin with its native and D-counterpart target
- MD trajectories of apo and amoxicillin-bound native and D-counterpart target

Background

In the mid of 1800 Louise Pastor pioneeringly opened the debate around the so-called *mirror life*, today referring to purely enantiomeric systems – e.g. *left-handed* carbohydrates and nucleotides, and *right-handed* proteins and amino acids (1, 2). Recently, Adamala *et al.* summarized and rationalized the major concerns a mirror organism may pose. In particular, the authors warned that mirror bacteria, i.e. enantiomeric microorganisms, may pose an unprecedented threat to life, as they are likely able to evade immune responses and exhibit enhanced fitness and antibiotic resistance (3). The authors also claimed for a broad and interdisciplinary engagement to foster a responsible and informed approach to managing a technology that may pose unprecedented risks.

In this context, we present our findings, methods, and raw data to offer a shared and completely open foothold to promote further research, driven by i) the necessity to approach this issue from an interdisciplinary standpoint, and ii) the critical importance of open, collaborative, and unrestricted science in the face of global threats to the biosphere.

Overview of amoxicillin in *wonderland*

We used our more-than-a-decade of experience in 3D protein modelling to study whether amoxicillin, a largely used antibiotic taken as a proof-of-principle, may interact with the D-counterpart of its target, i.e. the transpeptidase (TP) domain of the Penicillin-Binding Protein 3 (PBP3). In brief, we employed a simple yet effective method to monitor the geometrical stability of protein-ligand complexes to probe whether amoxicillin is likely to maintain its antibiotic activity in a mirror-image scenario. The quality of structural data is critical for these studies requiring high-resolution and as complete as possible structures,

which is why we studied the PBP3 TP domain of *Chlamydia trachomatis* (see the *Technical part: model generation and molecular docking* section). The L-protein-amoxicillin complex was studied integrating docking and molecular dynamics simulations (see below) as per previous studies (e.g. ref. (4-8)): as expected, the protein-ligand complex was stable during the whole simulation with the amoxicillin atom meant to covalently bind the protein stably facing the Ser320 side chain to form the bound (Figure 1 and 2). The D-counterpart of *C. trachomatis* PBP3 TP domain was generated through an *ad hoc* python script (see the *Technical part: model generation and molecular docking* section) inverting the sign of each atom coordinate, i.e. generating the precise mirror-image of the input protein and studied applying the same methodologies. However, amoxicillin should not favourably interact with the mirror-image of its target (Figure 1; see *Technical part: molecular dynamics simulations* section) opening debate on its actual effectiveness in a mirror life context.

Figure 1. Interaction of amoxicillin with the PBP3 TP domain and its mirror-image counterpart over time. The proteins are represented in surface, while amoxicillin in sticks with the time-step representation (red 0 ns, blue 100 ns). The two replicas for each system are shown. In the bottom close-ups, the amoxicillin's atom meant to form the covalent bond is shown as a sphere with the time-step representation (red 0 ns, blue 100 ns), while Ser320 side chain is shown in sticks. For simplicity, in the mirror-image protein, the time-step atom distribution is not shown for the replica where amoxicillin has completely detached.

Technical part: model generation and molecular docking

We applied here a consolidated and effective 3D molecular modelling pipeline widely used over the past years to study the interaction between small molecules and a variety of proteins (e.g. ref. (4, 6, 8)). The 3D structure of amoxicillin was retrieved from PubChem (<https://pubchem.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov>; CID 33613; Figure 2) (9), while the 3D structure of the amoxicillin's target PBP3 TP domain of *Chlamydia trachomatis* was retrieved from the Protein Data Bank (PDB ID 6I1F; www.rcsb.org) (10, 11).

Figure 2. 2D representation of amoxicillin. The red asterisk indicates the atom meant to covalently bind the Ser320's side chain.

The study focused on PBP3 TP domain of *C. trachomatis* since it was the unique target domain of amoxicillin available as high-resolution (1.89 Å) and fully resolved structure in PDB at the time of analysis (last database access 17th December 2024).

The 3D structure of the mirror-image PBP3 TP domain was generated using the following python script:

```
import sys

def invert_pdb_coordinates(pdb_file):
    """
    1. Reads a PDB file, inverts the signs of the x, y, z coordinates in HETATM and ATOM lines.
    2. Writes a new PDB file with inverted coordinates named with the same prefix and "_specular.pdb suffix".
    """
    specular_pdb_file = f'{pdb_file[:-4]}pecular.pdb'

    with open(pdb_file, 'r') as infile, open(specular_pdb_file, 'w') as outfile:
        for line in infile:
            if line.startswith('HETATM') or line.startswith('ATOM'):
                x = float(line[30:38])
                x = -x
                y = float(line[38:46])
                y = -y
                z = float(line[46:54])
                z = -z
                newline = f'{line[:30]}{x:8.3f}{y:8.3f}{z:8.3f}{line[54:]}' # line containing coordinates with
            inverted signs
            outfile.write(newline)
        else:
            outfile.write(line) # Write other lines unchanged

    print(f'Specular PDB file saved as {specular_pdb_file}')

if __name__ == '__main__':
    if len(sys.argv) != 2:
        print('Usage: python3 pdb_mirror.py <pdb_file.pdb>')
        sys.exit(1)

    pdb_file = sys.argv[1]
    invert_pdb_coordinates(pdb_file)
```

Then, after the geometrical stability of both models (expressed as Root-Mean Squared Deviation trend over time) was ascertained (see Figure 3 and *Technical part: molecular dynamics simulations* section below), the interaction with amoxicillin was studied through molecular docking first. Within the D-counterpart, due to the mirrored shape of the pocket, amoxicillin could not form the network of polar interactions saw in crystallographic studies and computed within the “natural” protein (Figure 4).

Figure 3. Carbon alpha RMSD plot of “natural” PBP3 TP domain and its mirror-image counterpart in the unbound state. The bold lines indicate the mean values of each measurement, while the shadings indicate the variability expressed as standard deviation over the two replicas.

Specifically, in both models, the binding architecture of amoxicillin at the binding site of PBP3 TP domain was calculated by means of docking simulations through the software GOLD (Genetic Optimization for Ligand Docking; v. 2022). The space available to arrange the ligand was defined within a 10 Å-radius sphere centred at the centroid of the pocket, set using the PyMol (version 2.5.0) command *centroid* on the amoxicillin in the PDB structure 6I1F. To reward the achievement of a as reliable as possible binding pose, the formation of the hydrogen bonds network described in the crystallographic structure 6I1F was promoted using the *H-Bond Constraints* option and setting the formation of polar interaction (with a constraint weight of 100 units) with Thr523, Glu527 and Tyr567. For each complex, ten poses were generated and only the best scored one according to the PLPScore score assignment (i.e. 42.19 units) was carried forth to the subsequent analysis as per previous studies (e.g. ref.(4, 7)).

Figure 4. Docking pose of amoxicillin (represented in white sticks) superimposed to its crystallographic pose (orange sticks) within the “natural” P3PB (on the left, green cartoon) and the docked pose within the PBP3 TP domain mirror-image counterpart (on the right, cyan cartoon). The yellow dashed lines indicate the polar contacts set in the docking simulations (and described in crystallographic studies), while the residues involved in polar contacts are represented in sticks.

As shown in Figure 4, the pose of amoxicillin calculated within the native target was superimposed to its crystallographic architecture retracing the H-bond network as per the PDB structure 6I1F, eventually supporting the model reliability. Conversely, the H-bond network described in the crystal was not kept while docking amoxicillin in the mirror-image PBP3 TP domain, though a slightly higher docking score was recorded (i.e. 51.17 units) and the orientation was comparable to that calculated within the “natural” protein (Figure 4). Positive scores should be proportional to the likeliness of the calculated pose, as per manufacturer declaration (<https://www.ccdc.cam.ac.uk>). Nevertheless, we previously demonstrated investigating further the interaction via molecular dynamics (MD) simulations may refine predictions providing more reliable outcomes (e.g. ref. (4, 5)).

Technical part: molecular dynamics simulations

The proteins in the unbound state, as well as the complexes generated by docking were used as input for 100 ns MD simulations using the software GROMACS (version 2022.6) (12) in agreement with previous studies (e.g. ref.(4-8)). Each simulation was done in duplicate. In brief, the proteins were parametrized with the CHARMM36 all-atom forcefield implemented in GROMACS (13) while amoxicillin with the same forcefield through the SwissParam webserver (<https://swissparam.ch/>) (14). Each system was placed in an octahedral box, solvated with SPC/E waters, and neutralized adding Na⁺ and Cl⁻ ions. Every system was then energetically minimized to avoid steric clashes or to correct improper geometries. This was achieved using a steepest descent algorithm with a maximum of 5 000 optimization steps. Each minimized system underwent isothermal (300 K, 2 ps coupling time) and isobaric (1 bar, 2 ps coupling time) simulations for 100 ps to allow the system to reach equilibrium. Once completed these steps, 100 ns long MD simulations were run.

As shown in Figure 3, both enantiomers in the unbound state reached the geometrical stability (i.e. a steady-state RMSD trend) through the course of the simulation underlining the geometrical stability of the “natural” PBP3, as expected, and of its mirror-image counterpart (from 60 ns onward).

Then, amoxicillin in complex with the “natural” target and its mirror-image counterpart was calculated following the same workflow drawing its capability to stably interact with the “natural” protein but not with its mirror-image counterpart. It was monitored the overall geometrical stability of the protein, the trajectories of amoxicillin in the two proteins over time, as well as the distances between the atom undergoing the reaction of amoxicillin (see Figure 2) and the Ser320’s side chain.

Figure 5. Carbon alpha RMSD plot of “natural” PBP3 TP domain and its mirror-image counterpart in complex with amoxicillin. The bold lines indicate the mean values of each measurement, while the shadings indicate the variability expressed as standard deviation over the two replicas.

As shown in Figure 5, the “natural” protein in complex with amoxicillin showed a stable RMSD trend during the whole simulation reflecting, as expected, its geometrical stability, in line with what observed when in the unbound state (Figure 3). Concerning the bound state of the mirror-image protein, the RMSD trend showed a slight worse stability compared to its unbound state (Figure 3) and the bound state of its “natural” counterpart (Figure 5), likely due to the not favoured and unstable interaction with amoxicillin. Indeed, within the “natural” protein, the amoxicillin atom meant to form the bond was kept stably close to the Ser320’s side chain in both replicas (mean distance of 3.2 nm; Figure 1 and 6). Conversely, in the mirror-image protein, amoxicillin early detached from the inner part of the binding site in both replicas showing a way wider distance compared to what described for the “natural” protein (Figure 1 and 6) which is not likely to enable the formation of the covalent bond, until detaching completely from the protein in one replica (see the main text for further details).

Figure 6. Distances between the amoxicillin's atom meant to form the covalent bond and the Ser320's side chain oxygen. The bold lines indicate the mean values of each measurement, while the shadings indicate the variability expressed as standard deviation over the two replicas.

Outlooks

Taken together, these results highlight the potential inability of amoxicillin to effectively interact with the mirror-image of its target, raising questions about its efficacy in a mirror-life scenario and urgently calling for further research. With this respect, *in silico* approaches may offer an effective first-line framework of analysis to systematically map the mirror-image proteins related to virulence, pathogenicity and pharmacological interventions that are likely to evade the immune systems and the currently available antibiotics.

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Addendum

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Extended MD simulations on D protein in the unbound state

The geometrical stability of the mirror protein in the unbound state has been further assessed by extending the MD simulations of both replicas to 400 ns. As shown in Figure A1, the protein stability was confirmed though a slight reassessment occurred (around 0.1 nm) and then keeping a steady trend from 250 ns onward.

Figure A1. Carbon alpha RMSD plot of mirror PBP3 TP domain in the unbound state. The bold lines indicate the mean values of each measurement, while the shadings indicate the variability expressed as standard deviation over the two replicas. To reduce noise, the alpha carbon RMSD has been calculated on the protein core avoiding random coil regions and those lateral whose secondary and tertiary structure depend on interactions with other domains not resolved in the structure used (i.e. residues 463 – 482 and 259 – 264 were not included).